

Wild Edible and Medicinal Plants of Santhal Pargana, Jharkhand

Field-documented species across Santhal Pargana — compiled under the Wild Food Forests Tribal in Jharkhand project

Use categories:		Wild food	Medicinal	Food + Medicinal	54 species 30+ families 150+ households surveyed	
#	Scientific name	Family	Local name (Santali / Hindi)	Part used	Use / documentation note	Category
1	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>	Asparagaceae	Satawar / Satawari	Root tuber	Reproductive tonic; galactagogue after childbirth; shady Sal slopes	Medicinal
2	<i>Asparagus densiflorus</i>	Asparagaceae	Satawari	Root	Tonic applications; moist valley pockets across Santhal Pargana	Medicinal
3	<i>Asparagus ascendens</i>	Asparagaceae	Parasi	Root	Diarrhoea, dysentery, worms; documented in tribal belt survey	Medicinal
4	<i>Dioscorea pentaphylla</i>	Dioscoreaceae	Ratalu / Jangli Aaloo	Tuber	Boiled as wild food during lean seasons; rock crevices and valley patches	Wild food
5	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Combretaceae	Harra	Fruit	Digestive and antioxidant; used in traditional medicine mixes	Food + Medicinal
6	<i>Shorea robusta</i>	Dipterocarpaceae	Sargom / Sarai / Sakhua	Resin, leaf, seed	Resin for wound healing; leaves as eco-plates; dominant canopy across hills	Food + Medicinal
7	<i>Madhuca longifolia</i>	Sapotaceae	Mahua	Flower, seed	Fermented ritual drink; seed oil for joint pain; lower hill forest margins	Food + Medicinal
8	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i>	Acanthaceae	Kalmegh	Whole plant	Antipyretic and anti-inflammatory; decoction for malaria	Medicinal
9	<i>Ricinus communis</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Arandi / Castor	Leaf, seed	Seed oil as purgative and lighting fuel; agro-forest edges	Medicinal
10	<i>Clerodendrum viscosum</i>	Lamiaceae	Bhat / Bhant	Leaf, stem	Paste applied on skin infections and snakebite; lower slopes near settlements	Medicinal
11	<i>Woodfordia fruticosa</i>	Lythraceae	Dhaw	Flower, bark	Malaria remedy; rocky stream margins and hill edges across region	Medicinal

12	<i>Boerhavia latifolia</i>	Nyctaginaceae	Chadgo	Root	Kala-azar; documented in tribal belt community survey	Medicinal
13	<i>Acalypha indica</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Ino	Leaf	Tuberculosis; documented across Santhal Pargana tribal communities	Medicinal
14	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Meliaceae	Neem	Whole plant	Skin disease; widely used across all surveyed communities	Medicinal
15	<i>Pongamia glabra</i>	Fabaceae	Karanj	Seed oil	Eczema treatment; agro-forest margin species	Medicinal

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16	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	Asteraceae	Puro / Gandhari	Whole plant	Eczema, snakebite; most commonly encountered herb at all study sites	Medicinal
17	<i>Lawsonia alba</i>	Lythraceae	Mehandi	Leaf	Snakebite; documented in tribal medicinal plant survey	Medicinal
18	<i>Rauwolfia serpentina</i>	Apocynaceae	Chand	Root	Snakebite; recorded in community knowledge survey	Medicinal
19	<i>Lantana camara</i>	Verbenaceae	Putus	Root	Elephantiasis, nerve disease; invasive but ethnobotanically significant	Medicinal
20	<i>Ichnocarpus frutescens</i>	Apocynaceae	Anantmul / Dudhi Latar	Root	Scabies, boils, wounds; shaded hill slopes across Santhal Pargana	Medicinal
21	<i>Butea monosperma</i>	Fabaceae	Bhelwa / Palash	Seed	Heart disease; documented in Santhal Pargana tribal belt	Medicinal
22	<i>Smilax macrophylla</i>	Smilacaceae	Ramdatwani	Root	Sexual disorder; documented in community knowledge survey	Medicinal
23	<i>Elephantopus scaber</i>	Asteraceae	Gobhi / Mayur Jhanti	Seed, whole plant	Filaria treatment; open hill patches and forest margins	Medicinal
24	<i>Argemone mexicana</i>	Papaveraceae	Atkiti	Root	Urinary tract infection; wastelands and disturbed habitats	Medicinal

25	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>	Amaranthaceae	Kaklaratha / Latjira	Root	Uterine applications; roadsides and open habitats across region	Medicinal
26	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Pusiota / Dudhi	Root, whole plant	Snakebite remedy; disturbed habitats across all study sites	Medicinal
27	<i>Tylophora asthmatica</i>	Apocynaceae	Bana	Root	Dental trouble, headache; climbing herb of forest margins	Medicinal
28	<i>Mimosa rubicaulis</i>	Fabaceae	Aru	Leaf	Blood dysentery; shrub of open rocky slopes	Medicinal
29	<i>Vitex peduncularis</i>	Lamiaceae	Kerkedo	Whole plant	Snakebite; hill forest margins and tribal homestead surroundings	Medicinal
30	<i>Vitex negundo</i>	Lamiaceae	Niswar / Nirgundi	Leaf	Headache; widely distributed shrub across Santhal Pargana	Medicinal
31	<i>Annona squamosa</i>	Annonaceae	Sarla / Sharifa	Seed	Antifertility applications; homestead and forest edge cultivation	Medicinal
32	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>	Lamiaceae	Bantulsi	Seed, leaf	Ringworm, blood purifier; cultivated and wild forms both recorded	Food + Medicinal
33	<i>Solanum xanthocarpum</i>	Solanaceae	Kattrangini / Bhatkatiya	Fruit	Asthma; open wastelands and field margins	Medicinal

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34	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i>	Apocynaceae	Aak / Madar	Stem bark	Joint swelling; dry open habitats across Santhal Pargana	Medicinal
35	<i>Guiera senegalensis</i>	Combretaceae	Buru	Whole plant	Skin disease; documented in community ethnobotany survey	Medicinal
36	<i>Agaricus bisporus</i>	Agaricaceae	Rugra / Mushroom	Whole fruiting body	Edible fungus; collected from forest floors during monsoon season	Wild food
37	<i>Amaranthus viridis</i>	Amaranthaceae	Jungali Chaulayi	Leaf	Leafy vegetable; gathered from fields and roadsides during monsoon	Wild food

38	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	Amaranthaceae	Bathuwa	Leaf	Cooked as leafy vegetable; winter weed of cultivated fields	Wild food
39	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i>	Oxalidaceae	Netho sag / Amrul	Leaf	Sour leafy green eaten raw or cooked; moist shaded habitats	Wild food
40	<i>Senna tora</i>	Fabaceae	Chakor / Chakoda	Leaf, seed	Leaves cooked as vegetable; seeds roasted as coffee substitute	Food + Medicinal
41	<i>Coccinia grandis</i>	Cucurbitaceae	Kundri / Tondli	Fruit, leaf	Fruit eaten as vegetable; forest edges and homesteads	Wild food
42	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i>	Apocynaceae	Anantmul	Root	Cooling tonic and blood purifier; most widely distributed species	Medicinal
43	<i>Flacourtia indica</i>	Salicaceae	Ramontchi / Konka	Fruit	Small tart fruit eaten fresh; shrub of rocky hill margins	Wild food
44	<i>Carissa spinarum</i>	Apocynaceae	Karanda	Fruit, leaf	Fruit eaten fresh and pickled; thorny shrub of dry rocky areas	Wild food
45	<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Bhumi Amla	Whole plant	Liver tonic and antidiabetic; moist disturbed ground	Medicinal
46	<i>Curcuma aromatica</i>	Zingiberaceae	Jangli Haldi	Rhizome	Wild turmeric; antiseptic paste for skin conditions; moist shaded slopes	Food + Medicinal
47	<i>Drimia indica</i>	Asparagaceae	Ban Piaz / Jangli Pyaz	Bulb	Traditional remedies; rocky hill outcrops across Santhal Pargana	Medicinal
48	<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i>	Apocynaceae	Koriya / Indrajav	Bark, seed	Dysentery and amoebic infections; mid-slope tree of mixed forests	Medicinal
49	<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i>	Vitaceae	Hadjod	Stem, leaf	Bone fracture healing; succulent climber of rocky outcrops and chatnari zones	Medicinal
50	<i>Marsilea minuta</i>	Marsileaceae	Sushni sag	Fronde	Aquatic fern eaten as leafy vegetable; seasonal wetlands and paddy fields	Wild food
51	<i>Flemingia strobilifera</i>	Fabaceae	Kanphuta / Mewa	Leaf, seed	Leaves used as fodder and green manure; seeds occasionally eaten	Food + Medicinal
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			Hindi)			
52	<i>Curculigo orchioides</i>	Hypoxidaceae	Kali Musli	Root tuber	Tonic and aphrodisiac; under-storey herb of Sal forest floor	Medicinal
53	<i>Arisaema heterophyllum</i>	Araceae	Jangli Suran / Cobra Lily	Corm	Corm eaten after boiling; rocky forest slopes and moist valleys	Wild food
54	<i>Vitis repanda</i>	Vitaceae	Pani Bel / Jangli Angur	Fruit, leaf	Wild grape; fruit eaten fresh; leaf used as a wrapper for food preparation	Food + Medicinal

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Project: Wild Food Forests Tribal in Jharkhand · Supported by The Pollination Project (TPP), USA

Documentation area: Across Santhal Pargana, Jharkhand, India

Note: All species documented through community surveys, field walks, and ethnobotanical interviews with Santhal and other tribal communities of Santhal Pargana. Data compiled with community consent.